

HEALTHY CHILDREN ARE OUR FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the health and well-being of the young generation, that is, people who are growing up or who are coming to the world and growing up in this country. Following the 7 important rules of a healthy lifestyle is the main goal of this topic. In addition, eating vitamin-rich products, paying attention to a healthy lifestyle, doing sports, and following hygiene rules are the main factors of living a healthy life

It would not be wrong to say that the slogan of a healthy child is concern for the mental, spiritual and physical health of the future generation and the growing generation.

The slogan of healthy mother and child should be one of the main concerns of every country, nation, and people. Because the future generation is the generation that determines the future of every state, country, nation, people. They are the seeds of hope for this people, country, state and nation.

If there is any creature in this bright world, everyone cares for their child, even carries grain in their mouths, feeds them, protects them and brings them to adulthood.

The human child, who was created as the greatest and most noble among all creatures, devotes his entire existence, if necessary, his entire life, for his happiness and future.

In this regard, our nation - the Uzbek people - is hardly enough. Seeing a child, raising it healthy, seeing happiness and success is the best dream, the highest happiness for our people.

It's not for nothing. Because the future of every family depends on what kind of child grows up in this family. The family is a small but extremely important link of society. So, the future of the whole country depends on the children of this country. That is why, from the days when Uzbekistan gained its independence, under the leadership of the President, thinking about the destiny of the nation, the future of the country, developing its legal foundations, and creating the necessary conditions were defined as one of the priority directions of state policy. Soon after we gained independence, the law "On the foundations of state policy regarding youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted at the initiative of the head of our country. The first order of independent Uzbekistan was called "For a healthy generation".

There is a saying in our people that goes in with milk, comes out with soul. The saying that it is halal like mother's milk is not said in vain. Therefore, the importance of mother's milk is very important for the child's future development as a person (without denying the role and importance of education).

From time immemorial, our people have treated the issue of genealogy very seriously and responsibly. During the time of Amir Temur, a lot of work was done in this regard. Sohibqiran attached special importance to this issue: "I paid attention to looking for a bride because I was worried about getting my sons, grandsons and relatives married. I saw this work as equal to state work. I inquired about the lineage of becoming a bride, the seven roses. I determined his health and physical maturity through special people. Only if the bride-to-be is free from all defects with her lineage, manners, health and strength, I gave a big wedding spectacle to the country and married her."

Six centuries later, Islam Karimov raised the issue of the nation's genealogy and healthy generation to the level of state policy. In almost every speech, the President focuses on the issue of healthy generation and youth. In the early years of independence, he put forward the idea that our children should be stronger, more educated, wiser and, of course, happier than us. The amount of work done for the healthy birth, growth, education, and adulthood of our children is enormous. It is not by chance that Uzbekistan ranks 9th among the countries that care the most about the health of the young generation in the rating compiled by the international organization "Let's Save the Children". It has not become.

In our country, the issue of a healthy child and a healthy generation is being approached comprehensively. In other words, for the birth of a healthy child, great attention is paid to the fact that the parents must be healthy first. In his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized that "A healthy child is the fruit of a healthy and united family, and a healthy child is born only from a healthy mother." kidded. This issue has been under special attention since the first years of our country's independence. In that report, the head of our state specifically noted this: "After we gained independence, we set the issue of raising a healthy and mature generation, first of all protecting family, motherhood and childhood, as the most important, priority task for us. we got it."

We can clearly see the practical proof of this in the example of the naming of years and the development and implementation of state programs on this basis. Year of Family, Year of Women, Year of Healthy Generation, Year of Mother and Child, Year of Health, Year of Youth, Year of Perfect Generation, Year of Healthy Child. At the heart of this is the issue of a healthy mother and a healthy child. The establishment of screening centers and perinatal centers is a clear example of the fact that special attention is being paid to the health of mothers and, at the same time, the health of the fetus.

According to the World Health Organization, 50-52% of a person's health depends on lifestyle, the food he eats, 20% on environmental influences, and 8-10% on the level of medical services. It can be seen that eating vitamin-rich products and paying attention to a healthy lifestyle are the main factors of living a healthy life.

The role of sports in the development of a child to be physically healthy, mentally fresh, strong-willed and determined is very important. Therefore, special attention is paid to the development of children's sports in our country. The fact that the Foundation for the Development of Children's Sports was created on the initiative of the President and the chairman of the board of sponsors of this foundation is the head of our country clearly shows how serious attention is being paid to this issue. Such a situation, that is, the establishment of a

special fund for the development of children's sports and the head of state himself being responsible for it, is not observed in any country of the world.

The following 7 most important rules of a healthy lifestyle are already known to us, but have been forgotten by the small worries of life.

1. Sports.

Sport is one of the main conditions for living a healthy life until the end of our life. He does not choose age, place, or even circumstances. It has many appearances, forms, and methods. There are types of yoga, pilates, walking, running, pull-ups, athletics, dancing, rafting, bodybuilding, gymnastics, football, etc. Choose what you want, as long as you are physically active. If you do sports for 30-60 minutes not every day, it is enough for you to be healthy. You need to sit less and move more. If your profession requires you to work sitting, take a break of at least 5 minutes every hour and do various light exercises during this time to tone your shoulders, back and legs.

2. Proper nutrition.

Include in your diet more natural products - fruits and vegetables, foods rich in vitamins and minerals. 65% of the diet should be fruits and vegetables, bread and various porridges, 30% should be meat and dairy products, and 5% should be allocated to sweets and fats. Food should be as fresh as possible, suitable for the season. More space should be reserved for plants in spring and summer, and for products rich in protein and fat in winter. Drink around 2 liters of water every day.

Avoid fast food, carbonated drinks, semi-finished products, chips and crackers, and many other foods with artificial flavors, colors and shapes.

Do not mix different foods when eating. Fruits should be consumed half an hour before meals, and tea and drinks should be consumed 1-2 hours later. After 19:00 it is allowed to eat only a little apple.

3. Harmful habits.

Open a wide path to a healthy lifestyle by giving up tobacco and alcohol products, which are the main enemies of our body, and various harmful habits. Every cigarette you don't smoke, every glass of vodka you don't drink is an important step towards a healthy life.

4. Agenda.

Strictly follow the schedule. First of all - 8 hours of sleep! Secondly, get used to sleeping at the same time of the day and waking up at a certain time! Sleep disturbance gradually damages a person's psyche and emotions, reduces the mood for work, and may later cause the development of various chronic and serious diseases.

5. Positive mood.

Another important rule of a healthy lifestyle is a bright and positive mood! Enjoy life more, don't pay too much attention to failure, bad luck, always find the strength to move forward and don't hold grudges, grudges, bad suspicions towards people, be forgiving, tolerant. Do not try to compare with the ignorant!

6. Fresh air.

Always keep your house, room and office clean, wipe it every day, open windows and provide fresh air. In order to be in a normal physical condition, it is necessary to know how to breathe deeply and correctly. Walking in the heart of nature, leaving the windows open for a certain period of time, doing physical work in the garden or in the open air is not enough.

7. Personal hygiene

Washing your hands before and after eating, brushing your teeth before sleeping and after eating, wearing clean clothes, and strict adherence to cleanliness in general are the main conditions of a healthy lifestyle.

Don't forget! A healthy lifestyle is a guarantee of health, strength and prevention of any diseases. It is a guarantee of success and development of various aspects of a person. A person who follows the rules of a healthy lifestyle will have a place in the family, work team, and society as a whole, learns to overcome various difficult situations and not to lose oneself in the face of life's difficulties. Just as a child has a duty to his parents, parents also have duties to a child. One of their duties is to raise the child healthy.

A healthy child should be understood not only physical, or only spiritual and mental health, but both.

Every parent should try to make their child grow up mentally and spiritually healthy and mature, physically fit and strong, free from various diseases and ailments. i must

Of course, with the raising of the slogan of a healthy child, every person of every category, every specialty in our country, on the basis of their knowledge, expertise and opinions, will implement this slogan in life, inculcate it and raise a healthy child. z must act to contribute. In fact, in order to give birth to such healthy children, their parents must be physically and mentally healthy. That is why in the teachings of our holy religion, it is important for a man to respect his wife, love her, and take care of her. Even family support, which is a responsible task in the household, is made a man's task. It is necessary for women to take care of their health and take care of their education by giving birth to a healthy generation, which is the future of the country. That is why it is very important to take care of women and do good to them. After all, in one of his hadiths, the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace, said:

"The best of you are the best of your people, and I am the best of your people."

To sum up, every service performed under the slogan of healthy mother and child is a service for the future of the entire nation, the entire state, and the national economy.

One more thing! The rules of a healthy lifestyle support each other, and one cannot exist without the other. By starting to implement them now instead of putting them off until tomorrow, we will take the first steps towards a healthy and happy life.

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